

Use of HPC facilities for European climate science: feedback from the CMIP5 experience

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Under the auspices of the World Climate Research Program WCRP, the climate modelling community organises international coordinated numerical experiments, named the Coupled Modelling Intercomparison Project (CMIP). These experiments form an important basis for the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Assessments Reports, which analyse model evaluation and projections of possible future climate change. The IPCC Assessment Reports provide one of the strongest influences on international policy from the scientific community. Indeed in 2007, the Nobel Peace prize was awarded jointly to IPCC and Al Gore Jr. "for their efforts to build up and disseminate greater knowledge about man-made climate change, and to lay the foundations for the measures that are needed to counteract such change". The community is now actively involved in the 6th phase of CMIP (CMIP6). We present here an analysis of the High Performance Computing (HPC) and associated data resources used for CMIP5 conducted in 2008-2013 by European climate modelling centres, and a first extrapolation for CMIP6.

Introduction

At a meeting in 2008 involving 20 climate modelling groups from around the world, the World Climate Research Programme's Working Group on Coupled Modelling (WGCM) agreed to promote a new set of coordinated climate model experiments. These experiments comprised the fifth phase of the Coupled Model Inter-comparison Project (CMIP5). CMIP5 was set to provide a multi-model context for:

- 1) Assessing the mechanisms responsible for model differences in poorly understood feedbacks associated with the carbon cycle and with clouds,
- 2) Examining climate "predictability" and exploring the ability of models to predict climate on decadal time scales, and, more generally,
- 3) Determining why similarly forced models produce a range of responses.

Strongly linked to the publication of the Fifth Assessment Report (AR5) of Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change in September 2013, the activity delivered an essential resource of coordinated datasets from a wide range of state-of-the-art climate models to answer questions that will have a significant impact on society in a changing climate. European scientists played a major role in this international activity.

The different centres started the development of their model configurations in 2008, some simulations began in 2010 and the bulk was realised in 2011. Seven European coupled climate models have contributed to CMIP5. The total European HPC resource used was approximately 50 Million core hours for approximately 100,000 simulated years and 7 PetaBytes of data were generated.

Analysis of the HPC used for CMIP5 and associated data requirements

The table in Appendix 1 shows a breakdown of the HPC resource used in CMIP5. Climate models provide particular challenges in terms of scalability and efficiency on modern architectures because of the inherent interdependencies across domains and algorithms (multi-physics, multi-scale codes). Therefore computing resource should not be measured in peak performance but in application performance. Lacking a good metric to compare the resources used by different models on different platforms and to extrapolate this utilisation to future machines, we express the total HPC resources consumed on a given machine normalized by peak and Linpack performance metrics. The Linpack benchmark has evolved as an industry standard to measure and compare platform performance and is recorded for all relevant computers in the Top500 list¹. Hence, it is possible to compare the compute resources used by the different groups in CMIP5 with the resources available at different Top500 sites.

Looking in the Top 500 list for a machine in Europe dedicated to climate science in November 2010 when the CMIP5 runs began, we can find the machine of DKRZ, the German Climate Computing Center. It delivered a Linpack performance of 115.9 TFlops (Tera Floating operations per second). About 20% of this machine was dedicated for one year to run the German contribution to AR5. Given the numbers in Appendix 1, it can be inferred that, the whole European contribution could have been theoretically run using the full machine in less than a year. Looking further down the list we can find the United Kingdom Met Office's IBM Power 6 delivering a Linpack performance of 51.9 TFlops. If entirely dedicated to running the European contribution to AR5, it would have taken over 2 years to complete the task on this platform. The Met Office contribution alone, of 5.7 Million core hours would have taken nearly 3 months of dedicated time using the whole machine. Of course, every compute centre involved has many more projects than CMIP. The conclusion we can draw from this is that national Climate Centres struggled to provide the resources necessary to undertake the CMIP5 exercise.

From Appendix 1, it can be inferred however that all European CMIP5 climate simulations could have been completed, in theory, in about 40 days using one machine with a peak performance of 1 PFlops in dedicated mode (24 hours a day, 7 days a week). This shows that even if national Tier 1 platforms gave adequately the resources for the core experiments of CMIP5, there was a potential for additional high-end experiments (e.g. higher resolution or larger ensembles) using Tier 0 machines.

When interpreting this theoretical number, however, we have to take into account some facts.

- 1) No machine is available all the time and is usually not available for one project only.
- 2) Climate models are highly complex software systems difficult to optimize even for a single computer system. So they take time to port to different systems. More importantly, they need to be validated on each computer system, a time consuming process usually requiring the simulation of thousands of model years.
- 3) Due to the nature of the problem, climate models have to run for very long integration times while having limited potential for "strong scaling"; so to simulate several thousand consecutive years only a fraction of our hypothetical 1-PFlops machine could be used and the run would last much longer than 40 days.

¹ <http://www.top500.org>

Consequently, to successfully prepare for and complete coordinated activities such as CMIP5 or CMIP6, the community requires stability of platforms for periods of about 3 years (6 month for testing, then 2.5 years to run the simulations). Clearly, this can be quicker if models have been ported and validated onto an equivalent HPC system. It should be noted that world class machines can move from the top of the Top500 list to the bottom in this period. As a result, the community working on programmes such as CMIP5 would benefit from access to a Tier-0 machine to realize integrations over a period of time during which the machine could become Tier-1. It is also important to note that not all HPC architectures and systems are suitable for climate science.

Furthermore, as can be seen from the table in Appendix 1, the experiments have very high data requirements (~7 PBytes in total for CMIP5). This data needs to be kept long term and post-processed and validated before it can be made available through confederated data portals.

To deliver results for CMIP6 in the 2017-19 time frame we need to be concerned now with the resources required for this exercise. We also need to keep in mind that the resources needed for CMIP6 will be close to two orders of magnitude higher those for CMIP5. And the challenges with data will continue.

It can be concluded that the CMIP5 coordinated activity was a very significant drain on the Tier 1 HPC resources directly available to the community. With more resource, we would have been able to increase a number of the key dimensions affecting the simulation fidelity:

- Resolution;
- Complexity, in including more earth system components to capture a wider range of climate feedbacks;
- Ensemble size.

Higher fidelity leads to reduced uncertainty and the science is ready to exploit greater resources today.

On the other hand, as detailed above, the most powerful Tier 0 machines in Europe would have been able to complete the task relatively comfortably if climate scientists could have reliably planned on access to resources. The capacity of computing was available in Europe and the models existed to achieve more than was achieved in CMIP5.

The Future of HPC for Climate Science in Europe

Today, Climate Science Programmes within major institutions rely, primarily, on locally funded HPC resources that are typically under high pressure. As discussed above, the EU climate community input to the CMIP5 programme was limited by available computing resources and thus not fully exploiting the potential of the climate community and its models. We strongly think that tailored access to Tier 0 resources would help the community to meet its full potential. Key elements would be:

- HPC systems designed to be suitable for climate models;
- Environments with long-term stability (~3 years);

- Support for high data storage volume/CPU-performance ratios. We can roughly evaluate that a volume of about 150 GBytes of data is produced per 1000 core-hours of calculation and needs to be stored, post-processed and possibly transferred.

The above analysis of CMIP5 lead to conclude that the equivalent of about 40 days of computing at ~1 PFlops peak performance would have allowed the EU climate community to complete the CMIP5 exercise. For CMIP6, we may project that the resource requirements will be between 50 and 100 times bigger and these plans are constrained by the availability of resources typically on Tier 1 machines or small proportions of Tier 0 machines. So we can extrapolate a figure of ~400 days of a 10 Pflops machine to cover an important part of the CMIP6 exercise (supposing that the models keep the same throughput/flops than for CMIP5) . Hence if the community was able to secure access to 53% of a 10 PFlops (peak) machine for 2 years, the available resources would be doubled which would lead to a material improvement in the output of the EU climate community for CMIP6; these extra resources would represent a considerable contribution for running additional high-end experiments with models at higher resolution and/or with more ensemble members.

Conclusion

European Climate science is computing-resource limited on Tier 1 platforms. The resources needed to significantly improve the situation represent a realistic proportion of a Tier 0 platform. Access to Tier 0 machines for CMIP experiments would significantly improve the European contribution by allowing the realisation of high-end experiments, either through increasing the spatial resolution and/or the size of ensembles, and would lead to increased societal benefit brought by more robust climate prediction.

Modeling center/contact from piControl/historical contact	Model	Number of simulated years (approx.) ⁱ	Dedicated computer used ⁱⁱ : 2009-2012	General purpose computer used ⁱⁱⁱ : 2009-2012	Data produced size ^{iv}	Total core hours (C)	Normalised peak utilisation (Pflops-hours) ^v	Normalised linpack utilisation (Pflops-hours) ^v
CMCC marcello.vichi@cmcc.it gualdi@bo.ingv.it	CMCC-CESM	1470	NEC SX-9 1 node (4 procs)	-	30 TB	40000 (SX-9)	104	98
	CMCC-CM	1570	NEC SX-9 3 nodes (48 procs), Dec2009-Jul2011 + IBM P575 1 node (64 cores Power6 4,7GHz)	1 IBM P575 node (64 cores Power6 4,7GHz) Aug2011-Jul2012	400 TB 70 TB	680000 (SX-9) + 780000 (IBM Power 6) = 1.46 million		
	CMCC-CMS	2680	May2010-Sept2011 NEC SX-9 2 nodes (26 procs)	-		250000 (SX-9)		
CNRM-CERFACS	CNRM-CM5	14000	part of Tori :		420 TB	1.17	19	19

contact.CMIP5@meteo.fr contact.CMIP5@cerfacs.fr Stephane.Senesi@meteo.fr Sophie.valcke@cerfacs.fr			NEC-SX8-MF_Other 256 procs			million		
EC-EARTH alastair.mckinstry@ichec.ie wilco.hazeleger@knmi.nl colin.jones@smhi.se camiel.severijns@knmi.nl shs@dmi.dk	EC-EARTH	14000	SunBlade ithaca (IC3) SGI Ice (ICHEC) Power6 ECMWF (KNMI) Cray XT5 (DMI) Ekman AMD Opteron cluster (SMHI)	MareNostrum II (IC3) LindGren Cray XE6 (SMHI)	900 TB	10.7 million on 7 different computers	103	85
IPSL ipsl-cmip5@ipsl.jussieu.fr	IPSL-CM5A-LR IPSL-CM5A-MR IPSL-CM5B-LR	20850 3440 1700	Mercure TGCC/CCRT/GE NCI : NEC SX-9 , 3 nodes, 48 procs, april 2009-dec 2012	And Vargas IDRIS : IBM Power6 And Titane TGCC : Bull Novascale	2 PB	1.3 million (dedicated) 10 millions (general purpose)	325	203

MOHC chris.d.jones@metoffice.gov.uk	HadCM3 HadGEM2-A HadGEM2-CC HadGEM2-ES	11350 850 620 5815	Met Office IBM Power 6 (1F) 3520 procs		1.4 PB	5.7 million	108	83
MPI-M cmip5-mpi-esm@dkrz.de legutke@dkrz.de	MPI-ESM-LR MPI-ESM-MR MPI-ESM-P	15277	part of blizzard: IBM Power 6 4 nodes a 64 cores 10 nodes a 64 cores 4 nodes a 64 cores; total of 1440 cores permanently in 2011		1,5 PB	12.6 million	236	180
NCC noresm-ncc@met.no	NorESM1-M NorESM1-ME	3000 1500		Hexagon Cray XT4 QuadCore 2.3 Ghz	200 TB	2.2 millions 1.4 million	33	26

Total		98122			6.92 PB		928 (or 39 Pflops days)	694 (or 29 Pflops days)
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ⁱ Including simulations for tuning the model

ⁱⁱ A dedicated computer is a computer dedicated to climate research

ⁱⁱⁱ A general purpose computer is a computer available for academic researchers through regular calls.

^{iv} Total disk space required for all data saved from CMIP5 runs (not just the data that went to the ESGF)

^v : The normalised peak utilisation in PFlop-hours is calculated as follows. For a given computer, we normalise the core-hours across different platforms by using peak performance as quoted in the Top 500 list. We divide the computer's peak performance (R_{Peak}) by the number of cores of the computer and multiply this by the core hours used (column 7). Similarly, the normalised linpack utilisation is calculated by dividing the computer's linpack performance (R_{Max}) by the number of cores of the computer and multiply this by the core hours used (column 7). R_{Peak} and R_{Max} expressed in Flops, are available in the Top 500 list (<http://www.top500.org/list>). Although not perfect, these « normalised » figures allow a better comparison across different machines.